

Improving long-term predictions of carbon and nutrient dynamics in Australia's agro-ecosystems

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Project Objectives

Long-term field experiments, and the archived information from them, offer the best and most practical means of understanding some of the most pressing problems facing ecologists, farmers and policy makers today. Several long-term, well-documented research trials exist in Australia's agroecosystems – regions that make up over 60% of the continental land mass and that represent areas where major vegetation and soil changes have occurred in association with agricultural activities. There have been large impacts on carbon and nutrient cycling in agricultural land, with some cultivated soils losing an estimated 39% of soil organic carbon from 1860 to 1990. Understanding these impacts offers an opportunity to influence future changes for productivity and environmental benefits.

The objective of the 'C & N Dynamics' Working Group was to address a critical need to make the data from selected long-term trials accessible in the form of high quality datasets for use in validation of mechanistic biophysical models. Predictive modelling of carbon and nutrient dynamics in vegetation and soils has become an urgent need to address community and industry concerns for environmental and economic sustainability and to inform climate change policy development. However, the value of model predictions is dependent on the capacity of models to accurately simulate observed responses to key natural and management drivers such as climate, cultivation practices, stocking rate and fire on soil properties, on the productive capacity of soils and on the wider environment, including greenhouse gas emissions. Validation datasets from long-term trials will provide the basis for building confidence in model outputs and for understanding any differences in outputs from different models which is critical for increasing their value for policy as well as for research and farm management applications.

Methods

Site selection: Four long-term research trials were selected for database development based on experimental treatments having been maintained for more than a decade with high quality monitoring of vegetation and soils and potential for access to data (Table 1).

Data collation and database development: Data custodians and field technicians worked with modelers and end users from policy and industry to assemble data and metadata for each site. This task was extremely time-consuming with experimental records in various forms from field notebooks to electronic spreadsheet files. Provision of data relied on approval of sponsor organizations and the capacity and good-will of data custodians for whom this task was additional to their normal research activities. It must be noted that future realisation of the inherent value in long-term research trials (that are declining in number) will be limited without recognition of, and investment in, data management. Essential model inputs include climate files, site characterization and experimental treatment information, and management schedules. A standardised file format was proposed for future development of more consistent datasets.

Simulation studies: Models trialed with the datasets from the long-term sites were Century, DayCent, GRASp, FullCAM/RothC variations and APSIM. Understanding differences between model simulations for the same site input data will facilitate identification of model improvements and policy applications.

Table 1: Long-term experimental trials used in the C&N Dynamics data development.

Site	Location	Treatments
Brigalow Catchment Study	40 Mha brigalow (<i>Acacia harpophylla</i>) bioregion, central QLD (24.81°S, 149.80°E)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1965 – 1982: pre-clearing calibration phase 1982: Clearing of 2 catchments-3 land uses (brigalow forest, cropping, grazed pasture; monitored for water balance, resource condition and productivity
Hermitage Cropping Trial	Warwick QLD 700mm/yr (28°12'S, 152° 06'E)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 43-years 1968-2011 Tillage, crop residue and fertiliser N practice treatments Measurements of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC), total N stocks, grain yields N₂O emissions measured under no-till
Kidman Springs Fire Regime Trial	Seasonally dry tropical woodland (16°05' S, 130°57' E) 620mm/yr	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1993: Trial established on 2 soil types: (1) calcareous Kandosol/Chromosol with native pastures, Eucalypts; (2) grey Vertosol with Chrysopogon-Eulalia-Dichanthium dominated pastures with Terminalia and Bauhinia. Factorial trial (4 fire frequency of 0, 2, 4, 6 yrs and early vs late dry season fire; 2 replicates)
Wambiana Grazing Trial	~70 km SW of Charters Towers, QLD (20° 34'S, 146° 07'E)	Operational grazing enterprise 5 stocking rate treatments (light, heavy rotational, variable, variable using Southern Oscillation Index)

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Major Findings

Improved understanding of data requirements: Preliminary results of carbon and nitrogen modeling for selected long-term agro-ecological trials emphasised the importance of collation of high quality data and metadata that includes:

- Initial conditions
- Treatment regimes
- Observation sequences for management and climate.

Long-term trials are expensive to maintain, and as the number actively maintained declines, the value of ensuring future access to comprehensive data becomes more urgent. Results reinforced that model validation should not be restricted to a single factor (e.g. soil carbon), but rather multiple constraints are needed to ensure the simulation of processes are correct (Carter et al. 2011, Parton et al. 2011).

Improving capacity to simulate observed carbon and nitrogen stocks and changes: Improved parameterization of the Century model for Kidman Springs fire experiment enabled better understanding of the interactions of burning, carbon stocks and productivity. Simulations suggest that regular burning to maintain low woody density and promote grass production will reduce above- and below-ground carbon stocks in the open woodland ecosystems of Australia's northern rangelands (Figure 1a; Hunt et al. 2012).

Preliminary model outputs for the Hermitage site using the DayCent model (Figure 1b) show that while the model tended to over-estimate grain yield (possibly because it did not account for crop factors such as disease, extreme weather events), it correctly demonstrated a positive correlation between soil carbon levels and nitrogen application, stubble retention and reduced tillage (Dalal and Reeves pers. com.).

Understanding strengths consistency of different process models: The national inventory model, FullCAM, soil carbon outputs were compared with those from DayCENT, Century and a Microsoft Excel version of RothC, initially for two sites, Hermitage and Wambiana. Preliminary results suggest little difference between outputs of the four models over the study period. Further, if input data are the same or very similar then all models appear to simulate soil carbon stocks to within 10 tC/ha (0-30 cm soil profile) of the final result based on a measured value of soil carbon stock (2010 site data) (Slattery pers. com.).

Figure 1:

a. Century modelling showing simulated organic carbon trajectories for the open woodland site at Kidman Springs for the tree (aboveground) and soil (to 30 cm) components and total system carbon from before pastoral settlement in 1900 and following implementation of three of the experimental fire regimes in 1993 (Hunt et al. 2012).

b. Total soil carbon under 12 treatments (2 x tillage, 2 x crop residue, 3 x fertiliser levels) showing that carbon levels increased with nitrogen additions, and was generally higher with stubble retention and under zero tillage (Dalal and Reeves pers. com.).

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Key papers and products

Carter J., Fraser G., Thornton C., Parton W., Henry B. (2013) Improving long-term predictions of carbon and nitrogen dynamics in Australia's agro-ecosystems. *TERN Symposium 18-21 February, Canberra*

Henry B.K., et al. (2012) New Value from old trials: Developing long-term agro-ecological trial datasets for C and N modeling. *Climate Change Research Strategies for Primary Industries Conference, 27-29 October, Melbourne.*

Henry B.K., Carter J., Conant R., Cowley R., Dalal R., Eckard R., Farquahson R., Gage S., Grace P., Hunt L., Moore A., Parton B., Reeves S., Rowlings D., Slattery B., Thornton C., Unkovich M. (*In preparation*) Synthesis of data from long-term agricultural trials for model applications: a case study for five Australian sites.

Hunt L.P., Liedloff A.C. and Eager R.W. (2012) Above- and below-ground carbon dynamics of different fire regimes in extensive grazing systems in northern Australia. *Australian Rangelands Society 17th Biennial Conference, 23-27 September 2012 Kununurra*

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science & management?

Measurement of soil carbon and nitrogen over the full range of geographical, climatic and management differences in Australia is prohibitively expensive and well-calibrated and validated process models offer a means of informing policy, research and industry decisions for management to address food security, ecosystem services and climate change objectives. Long-term field experiments (Poulton, 1996) provide the best source of data for understanding impacts of management and analysing scenarios for future management using process models.

Immediate benefits from the development of high quality accessible datasets will come from data improvements for Australia's national inventory and predictive model applications in land sector offset methodologies for Australia's Carbon Farming Initiative (DCCEE <http://www.climatechange.gov.au/cfi>).

Industry benefits will arise from improved understanding of the impacts on soil fertility and agricultural productivity of management options. Data from the Wambiana site have also shown a clear link between sustainable low stocking rates and increased profitability as well as better understanding of the relationship with soil organic carbon (O'Reagan *et al.* 2011).

The Brigalow Catchment Study (above) in the brigalow (*Acacia harpophylla*) bioregion of central Queensland commenced in 1965 with a pre-clearing calibration phase of 17 years to define the hydrology of three adjoining catchments 12–17 ha in size. Three land uses—brigalow forest, cropping, and grazed pasture—were established after two of the catchments were cleared in 1982. The catchments were monitored for water balance, resource condition and productivity. This trial provided data and scientific understanding on the interaction of climate, soils, water, land use and management across the three major land uses. Soil samples from the trial sites have been used in calibration of soil carbon modelling for use in estimating Australia's national greenhouse gas accounts.

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- O'Reagan P., Bushell J. and Holmes B. (2011). Managing for rainfall variability: long-term profitability of different grazing strategies in a northern Australian tropical savanna. *Animal Production Science* 51: 210–24.
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